

ELIXIR Commissioned Service [2024-SCIENCE-BFSP, WP4 - HARVEST: Handling and alignment of plant research FAIRification – value through the use of ELIXIR data Standards and Tools]

D 4.3: Preprint on plant data FAIRification

Tier: Science

Priority Area: Biodiversity, Food Security and Pathogens (BFSP)

Executive Summary

The HARVEST project aims to improve plant data access and reusability by implementing established data standards—specifically MIAPPE, ISA, ARC, and RO-Crate—on exemplar datasets. This deliverable, D4.3, constitutes the publication of the BioHackrXiv preprint from BioHackathon Europe 2025 (Project 28).

Work funded through the HARVEST project, along with its associated expertise and resources, directly contributed to the research and development presented in this preprint.

Entitled "Towards a Robust Validation Service for Data and Metadata in ARC RO-Crates," this report represents the culmination of HARVEST's technical efforts. It addresses the need for automated validation of both metadata (using SHACL) and actual research payload data (using Frictionless Data) within the RO-Crate framework. This validation layer is the machine-actionable component that ensures the FAIRness of datasets generated in the project.

While this preprint serves as the core output for D4.3, it builds upon technical foundations laid during previous BioHackathons and Commissioned Services of the ELIXIR Plant Sciences Community. These collective outcomes will be expanded and synthesized into a comprehensive peer-reviewed publication following the conclusion of the project.

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Abbreviations and Acronyms

ISA	Investigation S tudy A ssay Framework
RO-Crate	R esearch O bject C rate
ARC	A nnotated R esearch C ontext
MIAPPE	M inimum I nformation A bout P lant P henotyping E xperiments
FDO	F AIR D igital O bject
SHACL	S hapes C onstraint L anguage

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BioHackathon Europe Efforts

The primary output for this deliverable is the technical work conducted during [BioHackathon Europe 2025 \(Project 28\)](#). This effort focused on establishing a robust validation framework for ARC RO-Crates, which is a prerequisite for the automated indexing of datasets into portals like FAIDARE (HARVEST Activity 3).

Project 28: Towards a Robust Validation Service for Data and Metadata in ARC RO-Crates

As detailed in the attached preprint (Chadwick et al., 2025), the team delivered a two-pronged validation strategy:

1. **Metadata Validation (SHACL):** The team extended the rocrate-validator tool to support the specific profiles used in plant sciences. This ensures that the JSON-LD metadata correctly maps to the **ISA** and **MIAPPE** standards.
2. **Payload Data Validation (Frictionless):** Going beyond metadata, the project implemented validation for the data files (e.g. spreadsheets of phenotypic measurements). By integrating **Frictionless Data** specifications, the system can now verify that the data content matches the semantic description provided in the metadata. The Frictionless-based validation service is packaged as a deployable microservice on the [DataPLANT DataHUB](#), enabling it to automatically "check" the FAIR compliance of incoming datasets.

Outcomes and expected impact

Towards a Robust Validation Service for Data and Metadata in ARC RO-Crates (BioHackrXiv). This document serves as the technical specification for HARVEST's validation pipeline.

- **Trustworthy Data Indexing:** By integrating the proposed prototype validation services, the FAIDARE portal can ensure that indexed datasets are not just "available" but structurally valid and machine-readable FDOs.

- **Standardization of Quality Control:** This work provides a template for other ELIXIR communities to validate complex RO-Crates involving both metadata and raw data files.
- **Foundation for Publication:** This report, combined with the machine-actionability and tooling work from previous years, provides the complete technical narrative for a high-impact journal publication on the "FAIRification of Plant Data."

Dissemination Plans

1. **BioHackrXiv:** Immediate publication of the 2025 report as a preprint.
2. **Publication in a peer-reviewed journal:** A comprehensive paper synthesizing the validation work (2025) with the profile definitions (2024) and work on FAIRification of genotyping data from ELIXIR FONDUE will be submitted to a peer-reviewed journal.

References

rocrate-validator - <https://github.com/crs4/rocrate-validator>

Chadwick, E., et al. (2025). *BioHackEU25 report: Towards a Robust Validation Service for Data and Metadata in ARC RO-Crates*. BioHackrXiv. https://doi.org/10.37044/osf.io/zah28_v1

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Beier, S., & König, P. (2025). *BioHackGermany24 report: User-friendly ISA-based metadata annotation of life science experiments with ISA Wizard*. BioHackrXiv. https://doi.org/10.37044/osf.io/gzyxq_v1